

ORGANIZATION OF EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES IN MATHEMATICS IN PRIMARY CLASSES AND THEIR REQUIREMENTS

Almaszadə Gülsüm Siyavuş

Azərbaycan Dövlət Pedaqoji Kollecin müəllimi

email: galmaszade@gmail .com

Since the teaching of mathematics develops students' logical thinking, memory, attention, imagination, observation, will, independent and creative initiative, it is considered necessary to learn it perfectly from primary school.

Since the modern society has a great need for specialists with mathematical knowledge, it is necessary to cultivate interest in learning mathematics in students. In classes, this possibility is not wide. If we take into account that each lesson is the main educational goal, then we come to the conclusion that there is a great need for additional exercises and extracurricular activities to cultivate interest in mathematics as a concrete science.

Extracurricular work or exercise in mathematics complements, develops and deepens it as an integral part of the learning process. Therefore, the content of extracurricular activities for each class is determined on the basis of the mathematics program of that class and corresponds to the age characteristics of the students. Teaching aids for extracurricular activities include: textbooks, books and booklets for exercises.

Extracurricular activities (exercises) in mathematics serve to identify and reveal more capable and talented students and to cultivate interest and passion for mathematics in students.

During extra-curricular activities in mathematics, qualities such as love for work, willpower and organization are also brought up in students.

Class training differs from extracurricular training in the following features:

1. The lesson is conducted on the basis of the program and is mandatory for all students. In extracurricular activities, the teacher chooses the material himself and can deviate from the program.
2. Extracurricular activities are based on students' voluntariness, activity and initiative.
3. In extracurricular activities, the teacher applies the most subtle principles, taking into account the individual skills of students. At this time, the teacher not only gives directions, but also guides the students' activities, accustoms them to work independently, and directs their interest.

The following types of extracurricular activities in mathematics are applied in elementary grades:

1. Mathematical mornings or mathematical nights (mathematical nights).

Extracurricular activities have a special role in mastering and improving the quality of lessons, strengthening cooperation among students from elementary school, increasing students' interest in science and logical thinking, revealing and developing their skills. One of these exercises is spending nights on different subjects.

At night, students participate in teams. 4 or 5 teams are formed with one representative from each class. Teams are named from the beginning. In order to avoid discrimination, students of each participating class enter the hall separately, take the envelopes with the names given to the

teams, and sit at the team table with the name written inside the envelope. One of the envelopes also has the name of the group at the waiting table. Teams choose their own captain. The students of the group at the waiting table prepare behind to take the place of the loser. Judges, that is, teachers, sit at a separate table, and the "Evaluation Sheet" is hung on the wall near them.

2. Mathematical excursions.

In such excursions, students carry out work related to measurement and calculation in certain objects, and record the results in their notebooks.

3. Mathematical circles.

When the teacher organizes the association, the students learn problem solving, calculation techniques, measurement work, preparation of visual aids, etc. interest should be taken into account.

The activities of the associations are organized on the basis of the annual plan drawn up by the teacher and accepted and approved by the local education management bodies. In addition, the elementary school teacher's independence in organizing extracurricular activities and planning should not be taken away for the sake of consistency with the mathematics program. A teacher, including a primary school teacher, extracurricular activities, excursions, etc. It takes into account students' interest, level of understanding, acquisition of important mathematical skills, and elementary mathematics teaching material that cannot be achieved by any template planning.

4. Mathematical Olympiads.

Mathematics Olympiads organized at different levels have a special importance in raising the level of students' mathematical preparation and attracting them to independent study of mathematics.

Mathematical Olympiads are usually dedicated to solving problems and examples, quick and error-free calculation. Mathematical Olympiads are held in 3 stages. Olympiads in this style can be organized starting from III-IV classes of primary classes.

5. Mathematical competitions and quizzes.

Such events are considered mathematical competitions that can be organized easily. Their content may include theoretical questions, fun-logical issues. Mathematical competitions and quizzes give students the ability to freely express their thoughts.

6. Team competitions.

8-10 people can participate in each team in such competitions held between parallel classes of the primary course or within the class. Each team is given several problems and examples within a certain time (for example, 30 minutes). After the time is over, the works are presented to the teacher. After the tasks are checked, the winner is determined.

7. Mathematical newspapers and bulletins.

Information about interesting events in the field of mathematics, achievements of schoolchildren, including elementary school students, and mathematical innovations are included in those newspapers and bulletins. In order to express their thoughts independently, the information written by primary school students about the achievements can be highlighted here.

8. Mathematics corner.

A primary school teacher should always make effective use of the power of active students in his class. They actively participate in the preparation of visual aids. Handicrafts and various figures made by students are kept in the math corner.

In general, extracurricular activities in mathematics serve to expand and deepen students' mathematical knowledge.

Admission to extracurricular activities by classes is determined based on the application of students or their parents, taking into account their aptitudes and abilities, according to the order of the school administration.

The minimum number of students in extracurricular activities is 8, and the maximum number is 15. The management of the school is responsible for the effective activity of the organized associations. General management and supervision of the work of associations is included in the division of duties of one of the deputy directors. For extracurricular activities, a separate schedule is prepared by the deputy director of training and education and approved by the school director. Extracurricular activities are taught after school and are not scheduled. There is no evaluation for scheduled extracurricular activities.

Extracurricular activities in mathematics are non-compulsory activities conducted outside of school hours under the guidance of the teacher. Two types of extracurricular activities are distinguished:

- 1) exercises conducted with students who are lagging behind in mastering the educational material considered necessary to study in the program;
- 2) exercises conducted with students who have superior mathematical skills and enthusiasm compared to other students.

If necessary, extracurricular activities should be organized for each class with students who are lagging behind.

The main purpose of the extracurricular activities conducted with students who are lagging behind is to timely eliminate the problems in students' knowledge and skills in the school mathematics course. The following requirements are taken into account when conducting extracurricular activities with students who are lagging behind (it is also called optional or additional classes):

- 1) additional classes should be organized by separating backward, not too large groups of students of the same level;
- 2) in additional lessons, each student should be provided with an individual task, and each student should be given specific help during their performance;
- 3) additional exercises should be held no more than once a week;
- 4) after restudying a specific mathematical section in additional exercises, a final examination must be conducted;
- 5) when studying a specific mathematical section of each student, the reasons for his backwardness should be analyzed, etc.

The main goals of the exercises conducted with students who have a special desire to learn mathematics are as follows:

- 1) to arouse a lasting interest in learning mathematics in students and to develop this interest;

- 2) expand and deepen students' mathematical knowledge according to the requirements of the program;
- 3) to develop students' mathematical thinking;
- 4) teach students to work independently with textbooks and scientific-popular literature;
- 5) to expand and deepen students' ideas about the role and importance of mathematics in the development of science and technology, etc.

For elementary school students who have a great interest and ability to learn mathematics, it was noted that there are the following forms of extracurricular activities:

- math club;
- mathematical competition;
- Olympics, etc.

Math club is the most effective form of extracurricular activities. As a rule, students with a special interest in learning mathematics are attracted to the mathematics club. The classes of the mathematics club are held once a week throughout the academic year. Based on the topic of the materials studied in the mathematics club;

- life and work of famous mathematicians,
- interesting events from the history of the development of mathematics,
- organizes teaching materials that cannot be studied in depth in mathematics classes.

Similar to the rules of organization of all optional classes, clubs are organized on the basis of students' voluntariness. As a rule, associations are organized in the fields of science and art, artistic and technical creativity, sports, taking into account the inclination and interest of the students, as well as the appropriate educational material base in the school, and the provision of pedagogical personnel. A medical certificate about their health should be submitted for students who are involved in sports-oriented clubs.

The main purpose of organizing associations is to develop the existing potential of students, to create the necessary conditions for increasing the level of information, to expand the knowledge and skills they have acquired on the basis of educational programs, and to form their creativity and application skills.

Depending on its purpose and content, this or another association can be active for one or several academic years. Associations financed from the state budget are formed by students studying at the primary, general secondary and full secondary education levels. When these associations are being compiled, the interest, talent and intelligence of the students are taken into account, regardless of the class level.

The head of the association is appointed and released by the order of the school director. A document (diploma, certificate, etc.) confirming that the leader appointed to any association (a teacher or an expert invited from outside) has activities in accordance with the direction of the association is taken into account.

Clubs are held outside of class and on a schedule approved by the principal. A separate journal is provided for extracurricular activities. In that journal, there are special columns to record the list

of students' names, attendance and topics of the lessons, and registration is done by the head of the association.

The activities of the associations during the academic year (years) are evaluated according to the level of participation of the students in the events (exhibition, competition, competition, concert, Olympics, etc.) according to the purpose of the association. At the same time, in addition to the associations financed from the budget funds, paid and public associations can also be organized taking into account the mentioned requirements. During the organization of paid associations, the approval of the education department must be obtained, and a tripartite agreement on joint activities between the director, the head of the association and the education department is concluded, and the income from the association is transferred to the appropriate account.

Associations are organized in any school according to the staff unit (rate), staff schedule, and the number of class sets allocated to them. 1 class circle is taught 12 hours a week. If it is found that any loopholes are allowed in the teaching or organization of the clubs, an order can be issued by the school management to stop it. It should be noted that the organization of association or facultative exercises in the school within the framework of the law is one of the main requirements. During the organization of associations and facultatives, it is not allowed to ask for something illegal or violate the law.

When choosing material for extracurricular activities, it should be interesting to ensure the quality of the work. Extracurricular work cannot be replaced by repetition and reinforcement of general program material.

RESERCH

1. M.Sh. Hajiyev. Mathematics teaching methodology (general methodology, textbook for mathematics and mathematics-informatics majors). Nakhchivan 2017, 200 pages.
2. F.N. Ibrahimov. Lectures in general pedagogy, Baku, 2010, 390 pages.
3. S.S. Hamidov Methodology of teaching mathematics in elementary school classes. Baku, ADPU, 2008, 332 pages.
4. S.K. Mammadova. A textbook on the general methodology of teaching the elementary course of mathematics. Baku, "Science and Education", 2017, 130 pages.